

Google Scholar versus Semantic Scholar: a comparative evaluation

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Abstract

The rapid pace of technology has led to the development of countless of scientific databases and search engines. We compared and contrasted Google scholar and semantic scholar and asked whether or not semantic scholar should be adopted as the preferred database and scientific literature search engine. we ran an experiment, using a specific keyword in order to test the effectiveness of both databases and reported the results. Both databases were effective and displayed relevant search results in regards to our searched keyword, however Google scholar's search results filtering mechanism seemed very basic in comparison to semantic scholar's. Nevertheless, Google scholar has an advance search mechanism unlike semantic scholar, which seems to make up for its search result page filtering shortcomings.

Although the features of semantic scholar seems promising, we should not completely disregard Google scholar as semantic scholar is still in its infancy and it will take a few more development years in order to surpass Google scholar and become the supreme scientific literature search engine.

Keywords: Google scholar and Semantic scholar comparison, Scientific databases and search engine

1. Introduction

The development of the World Wide Web has helped engineered the foundation of an information society and it's widespread use has brought forth a digital revolution. Perhaps once of the most prominent example of such revolution is the development of scientific databases. in the past few decades, scientific records have shifted from paper to digital [1]. The field of medicine was one of the early adopters of scientific databases, the national library of medicine of the united state (NLM) introduced the first scientific searchable database called Medline in 1971 [2].

Fast-forward into the 21st century, digital scientific databases has become the *modus operandi* of searching scientific literature and retrieving information for academics and researchers alike. Since the launch of Medline in 1971, there has been a tremendous global effort in improving digital scientific databases and information retrieval system [3]. In November of 2004, Google Scholar, a digital scientific database, whose promised to bring academics and researchers access to vast amount of coverage of scientific literature and documents [4].

Given the rapid advancement of technology, exactly 11 years after Google scholar was launched, on November 2015 the announcement of yet another ground breaking scientific database and search engine was pub-

licised to the scientific community. This time they called it Semantic Scholar. Developed by the company AI2, Semantic scholar aims to focus on the semantic and textual understanding of documents, so that its users, when using the services can be presented with an understanding of a paper's content [5].

Given that Google Scholar and Semantic Scholar have their own characteristic and features, we aim in this article to evaluate, compare the two and investigate whether semantic Scholar should be adopted as the preferred scientific database and search engine for academic and researchers.

2. Methods

In order to correctly identify various features of each database and search engine, we used the official web page of Google Scholar and semantic Scholar to extract key information about each database and derived with a comparison table that illustrate key differences. the characteristics we chose to compare were the official launch date, supported language, field and period coverage, the ability to conduct citation analysis, the estimated number of document indexed and the ability to set notifications or alerts. In addition, we analysed the results of each database in retrieving information on a

specific topic that's been well studied in computer science. the topic chosen in our case was "**Support vector machine**". By using the keyword "**support vector machines**", on both Google Scholar and Semantic Scholar, we looked at the results of our search term and analysed the number of Journals and Articles it had found based on our searched query. we then proceeded further by narrowing down our search term by looking at specific Publication dates and analysed the results each search engine had retrieved.

3. Results

In table 1 we briefly compared various key features of Google scholar and semantic scholar. With Google scholar being the service that has been running the longest, it has amassed information and indexed more than 100 million scholarly papers across 14 different fields. This is in stark contrast to semantic scholar whose indexing capability only reaches 3 million scholarly papers across the field of computer science and Neuroscience and has been in service for less than 2 years. The stark contrast between Google scholar and Semantic scholar is not only visible in its indexing capability but in also the number of languages it can retrieve information. Google scholar being part of a very big and widely used World Wide Web search engine Google, it leverages its global popularity and it is able to search for scholarly papers in more than 50 different languages, whereas Semantic scholar officially only retrieves English language documents (according to semantic scholar frequently ask questions Page). Both databases and search engines are able to provide citation analysis. citation analysis is a method used to analysed the relative importance or impact of an author or publication [7]. To add to this, both Google scholar and semantic scholar are able to retrieve publications that dates back to the late 70's, while semantic scholar seems to limit its searches on the year 1975, it does not retrieve documents that were published before 1975. In contrast, Google scholar does not have a limit on publication period coverage. it can theoretically cover publications from previous centuries provided that the information is available publicly and it is in a digital format. [2]

Both Google scholar and semantic scholar have keyword filtering mechanism where various constraint are put in place to limit and narrow the search results. different criteria such as date of publication, authors names and types of journal can be used to retrieve a more precise search results from the database. unlike Google scholar, semantic scholar has a powerful filtering mechanism where each category in the filter options are cat-

egorised depending on the search results. Unlike semantic scholar, Google scholar includes an email notification alert system where researches can receive notifications when a publication that contains a specified keyword has been recently published.

3.1. Search Term Experiment

A search on the term "Support vector machine" evoked many thousands of results (15,000 to be exact) from Google scholar whereas only 26 search results were retrieved from semantic scholar. This suggest that given the keyword support vector machine and searching it on both databases and search engines, Semantic scholar was only able to retrieve roughly 0.17% of the results that Google scholar was able to retrieve.

In order to level the playing field, Google scholar advance search mechanism were used to narrow down the search results to only retrieve journal and article that has been published in the field of computer science between the year 2006 and 2016. The same setting were also set up and used on semantic scholar. Observing the results of both database and search engines, Google scholar was able to retrieved exactly 5,600 results while semantic scholar evoked only 17 search results when the keyword were searched under the same condition on both databases. This result highlights the major disadvantage semantic scholar has over Google scholar in terms of its ability to reach a wide variety of scholarly publications. In order to test the currency of each database and search engine, we used the same keyword we had previously searched for in order to be consistent and filtered the results to only display journals and articles that have been published this year. The outcome were similar to the results we had found earlier, Google scholar were still able to retrieve more recently published publication than its counterpart Semantic scholar.

4. Conclusion

A critical Analysis of the information and data about Google scholar and semantic scholar that we were able to collect and compare, suggest the following conclusions. The concept of having a database and search engine that cuts through the clutter, focuses on the semantic and meaning of scholarly papers will prove to be critical in the near future. many scientist and researchers would love to have such tool at their disposal because of its usefulness and its potential ability to save researchers some crucial time. However, to suggest or recommend the use of semantic scholar over Google scholar at this current time would prove to be a disaster as semantic

Table 1: Google Scholar and Semantic Scholar Feature Comparison

Features	Google Scholar	Semantic Scholar
Official Launch date	November 2004	November 2015
Language Coverage	English plus many other Languages	Primarily English
Field Coverage	Business, Economics & Management Chemical & Material Sciences Engineering & Computer Science Health & Medical Sciences Humanities, Literature, Arts & Social Science Physics & Mathematics	Computer Science & neuroscience
Period Coverage	Theoretically No Limit as long as it is available on the internet and in digital format	No availability for Documents that were produced before 1975
Citation Analysis	Yes	Yes
Estimated Number of Documents Index	100 Million [6]	3 Million [5]
Email Alert	Yes	No
Key word Filtering	Yes	Yes

scholar has not yet reached the development maturity or indexed enough publications on its database in order to compare and match against Google scholar.

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